

Supplementary Material S5.- GLM results showing the statistical significance ($P \leq 0.01$) of the interactions between the explanatory variables considered for each island and a dummy variable representing the Macaronesian bioregion. The response variable is constituted by the residuals of a regression between species richness and the number of published papers on the dung beetle fauna of each island. The Wald statistic was used to test the statistical significance of the regression coefficients based on maximum likelihood estimates. Island geological origin and island connection to continent during the Last Glacial Maximum are not included in the models because their values are all the same for Macaronesian islands (all of these islands are volcanic and were not connected to the continent during LGM). No Geotrupinae species have been reported from the Macaronesian islands.

		PCA temperature component	PCA evapotranspiration component	PCA aridity component	years since first human colonization	Human density	Area	Distance to mainland or large Island	Nearest continent	Maximum elevation
Scarabaeinae	Wald stat	14.80	12.85	4.78	30.75	0.56	0.47	0.24	0.09	0.04
	P	0.0001	0.0003	ns	<0.0001	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
Aphodiidae	Wald stat	4.25	19.15	0.75	24.74	1.25	0.26	3.42	13.94	7.81
	P	ns	<0.0001	ns	<0.0001	ns	ns	ns	0.0002	0.005